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**Teacher Attitudes towards Peer Review in EFL Writing:
A Qualitative Study**

Bjorn Fuisting

College of Business Administration

Ritsumeikan University

Osaka Ibaraki Campus

2-150 Iwakura-cho, Ibaraki,

Osaka 567-8570

Japan

Tel. +81-72-665-2090

bfr10087@fc.ritsumei.ac.jp

Brett Morgan, M.A. Ed

Faculty of Foreign Language Studies

Kansai University

3-35, Yamatecho 3-Chome, Suita,

Osaka 564-0073

Japan

Tel. +81-6-6368-0034

E-mail: morgan@kansai-u.ac.jp

Jeremy White

College of Information Science & Engineering

Ritsumeikan University

Biwako-Kusatsu Campus

1-1-1 Noji-higashi, Kusatsu,

Shiga 525-8577

Japan

Tel. +81-77-561-5202

jwhite@fc.ritsumei.ac.jp

Bio-Profiles:

FUISTING, Bjorn is a Full-time Lecturer at Ritsumeikan University, Japan. He has been teaching English as a Foreign Language for over 15 years in Japan and is enrolled in an EdD in TESOL at University of Exeter. His research interests include peer review, extensive reading and teacher professional identity.

MORGAN, Brett works as a full-time lecturer at Kansai University, Japan. He has been teaching English as a Foreign Language at high schools and universities in Japan and other Asian countries for over 20 years. His research interests include process writing, learner autonomy, and language learning motivation.

WHITE, Jeremy is an Associate Professor in the College of Information Science & Engineering at Ritsumeikan University, Japan. He has been teaching English as a Foreign Language in Japan for 15 years. He is currently studying for an PhD in CALL and game-based learning at Kyoto University.

Abstract

Peer review has become a common activity in second language writing classrooms in recent decades. However, the debate regarding its effectiveness is still ongoing. This paper is part of a collective case study into peer review usage at a large private university in Western Japan, and aims to explore some of the issues related to the use of peer review in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) writing classes. The paper investigates, through a series of interviews, what concerns teachers have about peer review that the university needs to take into account when training teachers and designing curriculum. The data from the study revealed that participants used both common methods to implement peer review as well as their own unique techniques. Several reoccurring successes, difficulties, and concerns are highlighted, as well as five underlying teacher beliefs.

Keywords: peer review, teacher attitudes, EFL writing classes, Japan

1. Introduction and Background

Recently the university where the researchers work added peer review to the curriculum of writing classes, but there is only moderate support material and no teacher training on the topic

has been conducted. Peer review is defined in this paper as “the process of students editing for mistakes and giving formative feedback on other students’ writing” (Morgan, Fuisting & White, 2014, p. 93). This paper aims to explore some of the issues related to the use of peer review in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) writing classes in the Japanese university teaching context. It is part of a collective case study into peer review usage at a large private university in Western Japan. This paper is the result of a small qualitative study using an Action Research model. The aim of the current study is to discover what concerns teachers have about peer review that the university needs to take into account when training teachers and designing curriculum.

This paper is divided into five sections. In the introduction the authors describe background to the study. That is followed by the theoretical background and literature review in section 2. Section 3 consists of the research design including the research questions. Section 4 contains the results. This is followed by the conclusions, discussions, and limitations of the study as well as possible areas for further research in section 5.

2. Theoretical Framework

Peer review is supported by two learning theories: Vygotsky’s *Zone of Proximal Development* (1978, 1986), and collaborative learning theory (Bruffee, 1984b; Hirvela, 1999). Vygotsky discovered that language learning is supported by social integrations based on the theory that learners studying with the aid of peers rather than alone can reach a higher level of development. He labelled this phenomenon the *Zone of Proximal Development*. In collaborative learning theory, students with differing abilities can overcome challenging tasks by cooperating with their peers. Collaborative learning was originally a tool for students to improve their learning and studies in a range of subjects in their L1 by discussing with and receiving feedback from their peers (Bruffee, 1984a). It has subsequently been applied to L2 learning as well, providing further theoretical support for using peer review in the language classroom.

2.1 Literature Review

Peer review has become a common activity in second language writing classrooms in recent decades. Advocates of peer review highlight its possibility to increase learner autonomy (Chaudron, 1984 as cited in Hyland & Hyland, 2006), support second language acquisition (Lockhart & Ng, 1995), reinforce audience awareness for the writer (Tsui & Ng, 2000), and enhance learners’ attitudes in regard to writing tasks (Min, 2005). In Asian countries, such as

China, Korea and Japan, such benefits are of considerable importance to counteract the prevalence of the grammar translation method (Gao, 2007; Kim & Kim; 2005, Richards & Rodgers, 2001) and the focus on passing specific language exams to enter university (Mills & Kennedy, 2013). Since university entrance exams in Japan usually do not include any essay writing component and instead make prospective students answer grammatical queries and complete translations tasks, students have limited experience in writing essays and paragraphs on free topics prior to starting their degree programmes (Mills & Kennedy, 2013). Thus, the increased audience awareness, improved attitude towards writing, and greater learner autonomy that peer review can provide could be considered particularly important in the Japanese university context.

Several studies into the attitudes of Japanese EFL students have shown that peer review is positively regarded by students and is seen as beneficial (Coomber & Silver; 2010, Morgan et al, 2014; Taferner, 2008; Wakabayashi, 2008). However, students have expressed concerns in regard to their own perceived ability to provide effective peer feedback to their classmates (Coomber & Silver, 2010; Morgan et al, 2014). Whilst Min (2005, 2006) has proven that peer review training and implantation can be done successfully in an EFL context, teachers in Japan, although generally positive to using peer review, perceive difficulties with training students in peer review and effectively implementing it in the classroom (White et al, 2014). Teachers also expressed concerns about peer review being compatible with their teaching beliefs (White et al, 2014). As a result, there is a need for further studies on the implementation of peer review and what teachers think about it.

3. Research Design

3.1 Research Questions

This study aims to answer the following research questions:

Q1) How do teachers implement peer review in their writing classes?

1a) Are there any common successful methods?

1b) Are there any common difficulties?

Q2) What are the underlying teacher beliefs that affect the usage of peer review in writing classes?

3.2 Research Methodology

This study is part of a wider collective case study into peer review attitudes and usage at a large private university in Western Japan conducted by the researchers. A collective case study is when multiple cases are included in one overall research study (Johnson & Christensen, 2014). In 2014 two papers were published by the researchers: A quantitative study of student attitudes towards peer review in EFL writing (Morgan et al), and a predominantly quantitative study into teacher attitudes towards peer review in EFL writing (White et al). The current follow-up study adheres to the 11-phase framework for action research developed by Burns (1999) and further explained in Burns, 2004 (p. 54).

1. exploring: feeling one's way into research topics
2. identifying: fact finding to begin refining the topic
3. planning: developing an action plan for gathering data
4. collecting data: using initial data-gathering techniques related to the action
5. analysing/reflecting: analysing data to stimulate early reflections
6. hypothesising/speculating: predicting based on analysis/reflection
7. intervening: changing and modifying teaching approaches
8. observing: noticing and reflecting on the outcomes of the changes
9. reporting: verbalising and theorising the processes and outcomes
10. writing: documenting accounts of the research
11. presenting: giving reports/presentations on the research

In action research the researcher identifies a problem, plans and conducts research to find out a method to overcome the problem, then implements the treatment and observes the result. This study could be seen as the first half of an action research project covering the first 5 phases. Through the researchers previous studies into peer review (White et al, 2014: Morgan et al, 2014), the feelings about the topic have been explored and a problem stemming from the addition of peer review to the curriculum has been identified, i.e. step 1 and 2 in Burns' framework. The research questions aim to discover how teachers have implemented peer review in their teaching situations and if there are any common successes and problems. In addition, the research questions intend to investigate what the underlying teacher beliefs that affect the usage of peer review in writing classes are (step 3). The semi-structured interviews and collection of material used in the implementation of peer review are step 4. After analyzing the results and reflecting on the data (step 5), the conclusion contains recommendations for interventions that could then, in a follow-up study, be further hypothesized, implemented and

observed to conclude the action research process.

3.3 Research Methods

In 2013, 41 English teachers at a private university in Western Japan participated in a questionnaire to gauge their experience of, and attitudes towards, peer review (White et al, 2014). To follow-up on that quantitative study by discovering the underlying factors, and to provide qualitative data, three semi-structured interviews of teachers working at the same university were conducted. Following an interview guide approach (Johnson & Christensen, 2014), specific open-ended questions around several themes were developed prior to the interview. This provided a good balance between covering the same general topics and questions and also allowing for enough flexibility to explore unforeseen themes that could emerge during the interview.

The initial themes for the interview were taken from the previously conducted teacher survey into teacher attitudes to peer review (White et al, 2014). Additional open-ended questions, as well as follow-up and probing questions, were formed following Kvale's guide to "Types of Interview Questions" (1996, pp. 133-135). The framework for the original teacher survey was based on a technology innovation research model developed by Rogers (1983) and Moore and Benbasat (1991). The themes in the survey referred to different aspects about implementing a teaching tool, in this case peer review. However, to gain more insight into the underlying reasons and feelings, the statements used in the survey were initially converted into open-ended questions and from that further developed. The draft questions were shared with two fellow teacher-researchers and refined based on their feedback. A pilot interview was conducted with a teacher at the university (it was recorded but not used in this study). After reviewing the pilot interview, the interview questions were again adjusted and an interview guide was put together. The interview guide was loosely followed, but as it was a semi-structured interview the order of the themes and questions depended on the answers given (Johnson & Christensen, 2014). Finally, additional follow-up questions and probes were used in the interview to explore emerging themes that had not been anticipated in the interview guide.

3.4 Research Participants

In order to get rich information about the area of research from a limited number of participants, purposeful sampling was used in this study (Patton, 2002). To investigate if the teachers had changed their behaviour based on revised curriculum guidelines that were introduced three years prior to the study, teachers were selected who had been teaching classes where peer

review either was mandatory and/or suggested at the university for longer than three years. In order to discover if there was any difference in how peer review was implemented for different levels of students, only teachers who had taught at least two different levels were included. Finally, to avoid any conflict of interest in relation to the participants feeling to be in a dependent position and thus possibly tailoring their answers to what they might perceive was a preferred answer, part-time teachers were excluded from this study. Following the selection criteria three full-time EFL teachers were identified and agreed to take part in the study.

To protect the anonymity of the participants the demographic details are not provided in a table form but rather in a summative paragraph. The three participants were all male, had all worked at the university for several years (four to six years), and had all taught multiple classes involving writing. The participants were all native English speakers who had been in Japan between nine and 14 years. They had taught English classes at between two and seven different universities in Japan and two of the participants had also had English teaching experience outside of Japan. They ranged in age from mid 30s to mid 40s. Two of the participants taught mainly in the Economics Faculty and the other participant had taught in both the Economics and the Business Faculties. Whilst the participating teachers would at times teach content classes, such as comparative culture, the majority of their classes were first and second year compulsory university EFL classes.

3.5 Data Collection

All of the interviews were conducted over a 5-day period. Prior to commencing the interviews, the interviewees received a briefing about the subject and purpose of the interview, and were given a written consent form to sign. The interviews were recorded and the data transferred to a password-protected computer. As the participants were native English speakers, the interviews were conducted in English by the principle researcher. The interviews lasted for 37, 42 and 53 minutes respectively, with an average of 44 minutes, and a total of 132 minutes. The interviews were transcribed using Nvivo 10 for Mac. The transcripts were then shown to the participants in a member check. Member checks are a vital step to ensure findings of an investigation capture the participants' perspectives (Neuman, 2014, p.84). As a further method of validating the data, the participants were asked to submit a peer review sheet that they used in the classroom or a document outlining their peer review procedure (Appendixes A-C). After each interview, an informal *debriefing* was held where more details about the purpose and design of the study were given and any questions the participants had were answered (Kavle, 1996).

3.6 Data Analysis

The data was analysed using thematic analysis. Braun and Clarke state that thematic analysis is a fundamental method that can provide “core skills that will be useful for conducting many other forms of qualitative analysis” (2006, p.78), whilst being flexible and having the potential to “provide a rich and detailed, yet complex, account of data” (2006, p.78). The qualitative software program Nvivo was used for analysing the transcripts. After completing the transcription, field notes and the research questions were used to do an initial coding of the entire data set. Potential themes, largely based on the research questions, were identified and reviewed to discover categories and codes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). During this process three main themes and ten categories and codes were created with a total of 120 nodes (see Appendix D for details). Once the coding was completed, a comparison of the different participants was conducted to look for common teacher beliefs and commonalities, and for differences in how they implemented peer review. Extracts that would illustrate the findings and relate them back to the research questions and the literature were selected. Based on that analysis, several conclusions, as well as limitations of the study, were drawn.

4. Results

The data from the study revealed that participants used both common methods to implement peer review as well as their own unique methods. Several common successes were highlighted as well as shared concerns. Also, five underlying teacher beliefs emerged from the data.

4.1 Research question one: Implementation of peer review

The basic schedule of conducting peer review was very similar among the three teachers, summed up by Bob (the names used are all pseudonyms):

So basically they write the paper, the first draft, and that is only peer reviewed. So they come to class, they submit it to peer review and they get their peers' check. Then their assignment that evening, or that week, is to fix what the peers have told them and resubmit a second draft and that goes directly to me on (the online learner management system used by the university). And that is the one that I check, and on (that) one I give a lot of feedback. I even go as far as sometimes rewriting sentences that I know that they will not be able to understand the grammar or anything, but really giving them a lot of feedback. And then they get one more chance a week later to submit the final paragraph.

The writing tasks assigned varied from class and level but were either practice paragraphs, such as opinion paragraphs, or essays, such as compare/contrast essays. The teachers used mainly a 3-draft process where the peer review was conducted on the first draft, teacher feedback was given on the second draft and then a third and final draft was submitted. The grades were either given on the final draft, or in Dave's case on the second draft, and then for the final draft "they hand it back in and then they can increase their grade. Usually most people do."

All three teachers gave students some instructions into what to look for in the peer review and all teachers adapted the instructions slightly depending on the class level and the writing assignment, but there were several broad similar categories. Bob described them as "I really try to break it down into three distinct steps, which is the format, the structure, and then the grammar." Greg described them as "I try to include in my peer review elements of all three, get them to provide some kind of feedback on structure and content and grammar." Dave also mentioned three categories: (a) layout/formatting, (b) structure and content, and (c) writing mechanics.

During the interview the teachers emphasized different aspects of what they asked students to look for during the peer review, but when looking at the peer review check sheets and procedure documents that the teachers had created, there was evidence of four categories:

Layout/formatting (Bob & Dave)

Structure (all)

Content (all, but in different ways)

Grammar/writing mechanics (all, but in different ways and to different degrees)

The naming of the categories and the groupings are slightly different, especially in how content was handled, with Bob placing the least emphasis on it and Greg the most. Also, Greg was the only participant who did not mention formatting of the assignment either during the interview or in the submitted documents. Due perhaps to the lack of familiarization with computers in Japanese high schools, many university students are still unfamiliar with formatting English text documents, resulting that the typed assignments the teachers at university receive are a bit like "getting a dog's breakfast" (Dave). Both Dave and Bob found peer review was a good way to get students to correct the formatting, with Bob stating "I get very few papers that don't have the right format and structure after I have done peer review". And Dave, while commenting on the effectiveness of peer review, said "maybe the most notable one is formatting". There were also other common successes amongst the teachers' peer review usage.

4.1.1 Research question 1a: Common successes.

The most common successful method when it came to peer review was to have students check for the structure of their peer's writing. All three participants asked students to check for "topic sentence, the support sentences, all that type of stuff" (Bob), and all reported at least partial success, "I am very confident that they can do that [check the structure]. And this is a good reminder, a good practice for them of that" (Bob). Greg stated, "I don't see any issue in terms of their ability why they can't do that [check the structure] with something their peers have written, usually" and Dave commenting, "I think it is good for the structure, topic sentence, concluding sentence, examples and details, and sequencers."

Even though all three participants reported success with checking the structure, all three used a different method for doing so. Greg had the peers copy down part of the writing structure that they were reviewing on his peer review sheet (Appendix B), whilst Dave had the students "go through and check or they'll sign their name or whatever and if it looks not good, they put an X or a comment in Japanese" on his checklist (Appendix D). Finally Bob stated:

I actually don't even use a form very often. I write everything up on the board. (...) They would be looking at the topic sentence, making sure there are support sentences with sequencers like first, second, third. And I write all those on the board to kind of remind students what that is and have them very quickly check that the students have all those parts and that they follow the correct structure.

When it came to grammar only two teachers reported having success with it. Greg stated: I think the students find it easier to look at grammar. Because that is what, to a lot of students, that is what learning a language is about, I think, a lot of the students we teach particularly, they think it is about learning grammar, writing correct sentences.

Even though Greg stated that he looked at grammar through peer review during the interview, it was not evident from the peer review form how he checked it other than the question "Are there any parts of the essay you can not understand? If 'yes', please put an asterisk (*) next to them and discuss them with the author" (Appendix B). Greg also mentioned that instead of peer review for grammar he had used a grammar workshop and states "the grammar workshop, though it was peer review in the sense that they were looking at each other's work, but the purpose of that was really to get them to think about those errors within their own work." Bob also seemed to take a similar workshop approach, but still using it within the peer review format for checking grammar "I just have them check the big ones and that cuts down a lot of work

that I have to do later on with those when I check the paragraphs.” On his procedure list he mentioned checking for capitalization and sentences beginning with SOBA (So, Or, But & And) (Appendix C). Dave reports less success with grammar:

I find the peer review process is not very effective, at least the grades I am teaching, the lower level, it is not effective at picking up the grammar or you know, capitalisation, basic stuff that would jump out at... at people... It just doesn't work.

Dave's mention of less success with lower levels was also echoed by the other teachers.

4.1.2 Research question 1b: Common difficulties.

There were several common difficulties with peer review reported by the participants. Whilst Dave clearly brings up the issues of low levels the strongest in his interview with statements like “I don't think it is very effective with lower level classes”, it is an issue mentioned by all three teachers to some degree, with Greg saying:

Of course, I think the lower down the levels you go, the harder it becomes, purely because the English, the quality of the English is getting lower. I mean, often I struggle to understand what the students are trying to say, so of course you can understand that their peers are also going to struggle.

However, on the subject of levels, Greg also states “I still think that most of them would be able to give some... some feedback of value to their partner.” Both Greg and Bob acknowledge the difficulties for lower levels to conduct peer review but also state that even lower levels can get something out of peer review “I definitely think at least the format and the structure” (Bob). A more severe difficulty was the feeling that some writing courses are too busy with requirements of teaching other skills, such as presentations, in the same course. Dave states, “other things factoring in too, like time constraints, curricular things so it [peer review] is not as effective as it could be.” Greg seems to be in agreement and states, “It was one semester only and I was doing presentations as well in the last three classes, and it was 35 students or something. So everything felt a bit rushed”. All three participants mentioned having difficulties with fitting everything in, but time was especially a concern that Dave held, exemplified by statements like “I think it's time. If we had more time, we could devote more time but we don't.” and “that is another problem, to effectively teach writing. It is jammed in with two other, three skills are jammed in a 15-week course”, as well as “So once again, I am repeating myself, it comes down to time. We don't have a lot of time to put in to peer review”.

Somewhat related to the issues of time constraint was the fact that peer review was considered to be unfamiliar to students and that they could be reluctant to comment on each other's writing. Greg claims, "Peer review in general, I think it is something that students are not very comfortable with when they first do it in Japan, definitely." He seemed to be supported by Bob "the first thing I found that is very difficult for students to do is to actually write on another student's paper." Also, Dave states, "It is not an automatic skill. I think it's not instinctive, I think they need some coaching."

Another less severe difficulty, but also agreed upon by the three participants, was that some aspects were out of reach to be addressed by peer review. One example given by Greg was in regard to coherence in an essay:

It is nice, like in an essay to refer... in the conclusion to refer back to connect back to the introduction. I don't think I've ever seen a peer reviewer make any comment about whether or not the writer has or hasn't done that. Because I think that is looking at too big a level for most to be focusing on. They are kind of more focusing sentence by sentence.

Bob also states:

When it comes more to, whether the paper flows correctly, or whether it really addresses the issue they are talking about, I think that it is very difficult for them and I think that is pretty understandable. Even in Japanese if they see a paragraph, I think at this level, they may not really be able to understand that so that is mainly what *I* do.

The four most common difficulties mentioned by the participants were; (a) lower levels not being able to conduct peer review effectively, (b) teachers not having enough time to devote to peer review, (c) the students being unfamiliar with the concept and procedure, and (d) that some aspects of writing are beyond even the highest level students to check through peer review.

4.2 Research question two: Underlying teacher beliefs that affect the usage of peer review

When analysing the transcripts, five underlying teacher beliefs that could be said to affect the usage of peer review in writing classes were found in the data. Firstly, it seemed that all three participants would describe their classes as student-centered. Greg says "everybody says this but my classes are student-centered". The focus on group work in the participants' classes was also evident, highlighted by Dave's comment "I think, collaborative activities work well, so in

terms of do I believe that students helping each other works, of course I think it's great". The fact that all the teachers interviewed in general favored group work and student-focused classes meant that peer review fitted in with their teaching style. Secondly, and related to the first point, is the fact that the participants believed using peer review in their writing classes was beneficial even though they at times expressed doubts. Maybe Dave sums it up best "I don't know how much it is helping, but I think it is helping, so that's why I try and do it in some shape or form in my writing classes". This belief in the effectiveness of peer review was not limited to writing classes.

The third shared belief was that the teachers in the study all employed peer review for teaching other skills, such as presentations, with Bob stating "I definitely do it for the presentations". Dave even went as far as to claim that "the peer review process works much, much better for a presentation than it does for a writing activity". Another belief that the teachers shared were that they all stated that they enjoyed teaching writing, evident by statements such as "I really enjoy teaching the writing classes" by Bob. Finally, the participants shared a belief that students should be allowed to use their L1 for certain classroom activities. Dave explains his view:

If they want to use some Japanese, especially for peer review, if they are on task, they are not talking about, you know, AKB48 (a Japanese pop group) or something, then I'm fine with that. I think it is probably beneficial for them to get some peer review in their own language.

These teacher beliefs put together, especially the first three of having student-centered classes, believing in the effectiveness of peer review for EFL writing, and having had other positive experiences using peer review, seem to make a teacher more likely to use peer review in writing classes.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

Peer review can be done in various ways and with varied levels of success, but both the literature and the participants in this study seem to support its inclusion in EFL writing classes. All three teachers used peer review in their classes and believed it had at least some positive effect on their students' writing, especially in regard to the structure. Other perceived benefits of peer review varied from teacher to teacher and were also influenced by the class level, class size, and curricular burden. Also, four underlying teacher beliefs were found to exist in the participants. They all stated that they enjoyed teaching writing, had a student-focused approach, believed that peer review worked both in writing and other classes, and that they allowed students to conduct peer review in their L1.

Based on the themes coming from the interviews, the researchers can attempt to make some recommendations. If an institution asks teachers to incorporate peer review in their writing classes, one of the key things is to make time for it. Min (2005, 2006) has shown that training students can improve the effectiveness of peer review. However, in her study a considerable amount of outside class one-on-one training and follow-up was conducted, which might be beyond what most teachers can be expected to provide. Therefore, if peer review is added to an existing class that is already considered to have a busy schedule, then something else had better be taken out in order not to overburden the students and teachers. This was also evident from the teacher survey done by White et al (2014). From the interviews there seems to be evidence that this is particularly important in courses that teach skills in addition to writing. In such mixed skills courses, using peer review for other tasks, such as presentations, might lead to a more positive impression of peer review in general and thus, possibly, a higher uptake among teachers when it comes to writing.

Based on the participants' experiences, it also seems like it might be better to allow individual teachers to adjust any peer review check sheets or procedures that are used with the teaching material. Rather than relying on standardised forms in writing texts, providing teachers with an editable electronic copy of the peer review check sheets could lessen the risk of students being confused by differences in terminology between teachers and thus lead to more effective peer review. This is a relatively simple step that subject coordinators could aim to do.

Something that also emerged out of the interviews was that peer review could not deal with all issues in all writing classes. The level and size of class seemed to impact the effectiveness of peer review. Therefore, it could be argued that teachers need to be clear what they want students to check through peer review and what should be left for teacher feedback. Zhang (1995) has shown that students prefer teacher feedback to peer feedback, but if they are aware that they will receive teacher feedback in addition to student peer review they are more positive to doing peer review (Jacobs, Curtis & Huang, 1998). The peer review tasks might also work better if the teachers can tie the activity to either extrinsic rewards such as participation marks, or intrinsic rewards such as highlighting the learning opportunity that peer review could provide. Lundstrom and Baker have shown that learners who have experienced peer review also improve their own writing (2009). Making the peer review tasks specific, suitable, and relevant would likely lead to greater student involvement. Finally, although many teaching institutions and teachers in Japan and Asian countries aim to use only the target language during language classes, it might be more effective not to apply this rule to peer review tasks but to instead encourage students to use their L1 during peer review.

Following Burn's (2004) action research framework, an intervention in the form of a teacher workshop on peer review implementation could be conducted at the university in this study. This workshop could summarise the findings of the two previous quantitative studies (White et al, 2014; Morgan et al, 2014) as well as the current study to increase awareness of the situation. A variety of peer review check sheets could also be distributed, both in paper and electronic form, and practised. Individual teachers could be encouraged to adapt these forms. Guidelines to include peer review as a part of the writing grade could also be suggested. This might lead to both students and teachers giving more attention to the peer review activities. If such a workshop was to be conducted prior to the semester starting it could possibly be followed by collecting feedback about teachers' peer review experiences, in the form of surveys, focus groups and/or interviews, from the teachers involved at the end of the semester. While this study has a Japanese university focus, it is clear that other countries both within Asia and elsewhere around the world might encounter similar successes and challenges with peer review. All educators who currently do, or want to develop, peer review within their institution could find the aforementioned recommendations a useful resource for their own endeavours.

5.1 Pedagogical Implication

This study has some obvious pedagogical implications for future of peer review in the Japanese university classroom. Those who are responsible for developing curricula will need to take into account the teaching approaches of all within their group, while focusing on the main points that peer review can successfully achieve in a classroom environment. With the environment being one of continual change, due to limited term contracts, this process of developing and refining peer review will need to be continuous to ensure the inclusion of all members within the teaching environment. Failure to do so may lead to a sense of animosity from those entering into the teaching environment but without a voice in the development of the curricula.

5.2 Limitations and Suggestions for Further Research

Although being members of the teaching institution in which the study took place was beneficial as far as understanding the circumstances and having shared experiences with the interviewees, it also posed a risk of the researcher being biased and having a vested interest in the outcome of the study. In order to minimise this risk, the interview questions were constructed to be neutral and open-ended, and the researchers took care not to attempt to lead the participants when prompting or asking follow-up questions.

Furthermore, this study was limited by the small number of teachers that took part in the interview as well as by the limited interview occasions. To achieve a more generalisable result the study would have needed to include a greater number of participants and possibly have had reoccurring interviews. Also, to achieve a greater degree of validity, the study could have aimed to include both classroom observations and student interviews, both of which present opportunities for further research that could lead to a better understanding of the subject.

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Appendix A: Greg's Peer Review Check Sheet

Peer Review: Introduction and Body Paragraphs

Your name: _____
Partner's name: _____
Essay title: _____

A. Switch introductions with a partner. Read your partner's introduction and body . In the space below write something that you liked about it.

B. Read the introduction and body and answer the following questions:

1) What is the writer's main point in this essay?

2) Does the introduction have a good hook? Please explain your answer

3) Does the introduction have enough background information? If not, what other information could the author add?

4) Does the thesis statement clearly show the author's opinion? If 'yes', what is the author's opinion?

5) Does the thesis statement show the main point of each body paragraph? If 'yes', what are the main points?

- a. Body 1: _____
- b. Body 2: _____
- c. Body 3: _____

6) Does each body paragraph focus clearly on **one** main point? If 'no', please explain why you think so.

7) Does each body paragraph have a clear topic sentence which shows the main point? If 'no', please explain why you think so.

8) Does each body paragraph have enough support? If 'no', please explain why you think so. _____

9) Does each body paragraph have a concluding sentence? If 'no', please explain why you think so. ____

10) Are there any parts of the essay you can not understand? If 'yes', please put an asterisk* next to them and discuss them with the author.

11) Do you have any suggestions for the author?

Appendix B: Bob's Peer Review Process

Peer Review Process

1. Read and question
 - a. Read the paper and write a question about it on the back
 - b. Ask your partner the question and write their answer down

2. Format
 - a. Check the heading – name, student number, class, and date
 - b. Double space
 - c. 12-point font Times New Roman
 - d. Title underlined

3. Structure
 - a. Topic sentence
 - b. Support sentences (1-3 with sequencers)
 - c. Details and examples
 - d. Concluding sentence

4. Grammar
 - a. Check for SOBA
 - b. Check for correct capitalization

Appendix C: Dave's Peer Review Check Sheet

Writing assignment -- Self-check & Peer-check

What should I check?	Self-check	Peer-check Name: _____
Formatting Student information is correct (<i>name, student number, class, date</i>) Student information - right alignment Times New Roman font Font size - 12 point Word count (bottom right) Title - bold & centered Double spaced Indent - new paragraphs left alignment (or 'justify text') Paragraph sentences - spacing. (Don't start sentences on new lines)		
Introduction There is a topic sentence / Thesis statement		
Body		

There are main supporting sentences . Ways to solve the problem Advantages / disadvantages		
Body Details & examples - support the main sentences.		
Conclusion Restates the ideas from topic sentence in different words. Prediction about the solutions / future.		
Writing mechanics & style There is effective language use. The sentences are well written and clear. (It is easy to understand) There are limited errors (spelling, punctuation) The sentences are not too long or too short.		

Appendix D: Coding scheme

Table 1: Coding scheme

Themes	Categories & Codes	Sources	References
Difficulties		3	45
	Too busy	3	11
	Too low level	3	9
	Unfamiliar	3	5
Successful implementation		3	44
	Structure	3	10
	Not too low level	3	8
	Grammar	2	6
	Layout/formatting	2	6
Underlying teacher beliefs		3	31
	Believe in peer review	3	4
	Enjoy teaching writing	3	4
	Student-centered	2	4
	L1 usage	2	3